

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF LITERATURE OF MICRO AND TINY FINANCE WITH THE HELP OF MFIs AND SHGs IN INDIA

Ms Neha Saini¹, Dr. O P Pathak²

¹Research Scholar, Institute of Engineering & Technology Alwar (Raj.)

²Head, Department of Management Studies, Institute of Engineering & Technology Alwar (Raj.)

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ABSTRACT

Indian economy is characterized by low rate of growth, dominance of rural population, heavy dependency on agriculture, adverse land mass ratio, highly skewed distribution of income and wealth beside, high incidence of poverty unemployment and poverty. The last two factors poverty and unemployment pose major challenges to the growth and prosperity of the country. To overcome this problem, some newly developed sectors like micro finance are playing a vital role. Microfinance has been considered a powerful tool to fight poverty through the provision of basic financial services including savings, insurance, credit and transfer of funds. The objective of microfinance institutions is to serve poor people and enable them to access credit and fight poverty. Against such improvements, the present study has been carried out to study of review literature in microfinance sector.

Key words: Economy, India, Micro, Tiny, Finance

REVIEW OF LITERATURE OF MICRO AND TINY FINANCE

Prof. (Ms.) Gazia Sayed, Dr. Pankaj Trivedi

“Role of Micro Finance Institutions in Development of Micro-Enterprises (MSMEs) in Mumbai - An Empirical Study” This research paper is based on the evolution of microfinance institutions (MFIs) and their Contribution to the development of Micro-Enterprise viz. micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs) in Mumbai. This study sought to fill in the gap by examining the impact of microfinance institutions on growth and development of small and medium enterprises. A survey was conducted on 110 SME owners using structured questionnaire. Data from the respondents was analyzed and translated into useful information using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Frequency distributions, Crosstabs and Chi square were used to draw conclusions. The study established that 85 SMEs out of 110 SMEs surveyed obtained credit from MFIs. Results show that increased on business sales volume, profits and physical assets are the impact of adequate microfinance access (statistically significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significant). Statistically the finding shows that the increased of business capital structure has no direct relationship with microfinance access (insignificant by 0.104 when $P \leq 0.05$ level of significant).

Vipin kumar, Monu chauhan, Ritesh kumar (2013)

“An overview of microfinance in India” In a country like India where 70 percent of its population lives in rural area and 60 percent depend on agriculture (according to the World Bank reports), micro-finance can play a vital role in providing financial services to the poor and low income individuals. Microfinance is the form of a broad range of financial services such as deposits, loans, payment services, money transfers, insurance, savings, micro-credit etc. to the poor and low income individuals. The importance of micro-finance in the developing economies like India cannot be undermined, where a large size of population is living under poverty and large number of people does not have an access to formal banking facilities. The taskforce on Supportive Policy and Regulatory Framework for Microfinance constituted by NABARD defined microfinance as “ the provision of thrift, saving, credit and financial services and products of very small amount to the poor’s in rural, semi urban and urban areas for enabling them to raise their income level and improve their standard of living.” (Sen, 2008) Micro-finance is regarded as a useful tool for socio-economic up-liftmen in a developing country like India. It is expected to play a significant role in poverty alleviation and development. There are two broad approaches that characterize the microfinance sector in India is Self Help Groups (SHGs)-Bank linkage programme and Microfinance Institution (MFIs). In India microfinance is dominated by Self Help Groups (SHGs)-Bank linkage programme aimed at providing a cost effective mechanism for providing financial services to the unreached poor. The present paper aims at identifying the current status and role of microfinance in the development of India.

Manish Kumar, Narendra Singh Bohra and Amar Johari (2010)

“Micro-Finance as an Anti Poverty Vaccine for Rural India” India falls under low income class according to World Bank. It is second populated country in the world and around 70 % of its population lives in rural area. 60% of people depend on agriculture, as a result there is chronic underemployment and per capita income is only \$ 3262. This is not enough to provide food to more than one individual. The obvious result is abject poverty, low rate of education, low sex ratio, and exploitation. The major factor account for high incidence of rural poverty is the low asset base. According to Reserve Bank of India, about 51 % of people house possess only 10% of the total asset of India .This has resulted low production capacity both in agriculture (which contribute around 22-25% of GDP) and Manufacturing sector. Rural people have very low access to institutionalized credit from commercial bank.

Dr. Prasann Kumar Das (2014)

“Microfinance - A Tool for Socio – Economic Development in Rural India” Microfinance stands as one of the most promising and cost effective tools which fight against global poverty. The findings from this study suggests that there is rise in the history and perspectives of rural credit in India in form of microfinance and there is need for improved governance to manage challenges for future so that socio-economic growth is possible. The present paper discusses conceptual framework, development process, growth of SHG linked microfinance programme, types of micro finance services and developmental role of these institutions in rural India. It also focuses on the status of microfinance and provides some policy framework to meet the challenges faced by Indian microfinance. The article traces that the evolution of the microfinance revolution in India as a powerful tool for socio-economic development in rural India.

Ms. R. Sunitha Shree

“Research works on impact of microfinance on development of micro and small enterprises”. Microfinance emerged as a noble substitute for informal credit and an effective and Powerful instrument for poverty reduction among people, who are economically active, but financially constrained and vulnerable in various countries. Microfinance covers a broad range of financial services including loans, deposits and payment services and insurance to the poor and low-income households and their micro enterprises. Microfinance institutions have shown a significant contribution towards the poor in rural, semi urban or urban areas for enabling them to raise their income level and living standards in various countries. In developing countries like India the structure of economy is dualistic. The rich get richer and the poor get poorer. This worsens the access of poor to economic opportunities and reaches for formal financial services. Small enterprises in India suffer from a great deal of indebtedness and are subject to exploitation in the credit market through high interest rates and lack of convenient access to credit. They need credit to fund their working capital needs on a day-to-day basis as well as long term needs like emergencies or other income related activities. So the need for financial assistance and business development services for the micro and small enterprises is essential to alleviate poverty for consistent economic growth. The focus of the study is to find out whether these micro and small enterprises in and around Coimbatore city of Tamil Nadu were able to access Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) for capital loans and services and utilize it for their growth and development

Madhubala swami,

“A critical study of self-help groups and their microfinance activity in thane city” Self-help groups in Thane city represent a slice of the urban poor. Promoted by different agencies (SHPIs) these SHGs display distinct socio economic profile of the urban poor. The present study is undertaken with the main objective of examining the microfinance activities of self-help groups, affiliated or non-affiliated to an SHPI in Thane city. It has been found that these SHGs operate more or less like ROSCAs except for the fact that they are registered with a government body (TMC). Unlike their counterpart in the South Indian states, they are not organized into larger federations, have limited linkage with the financial institutions such as banks or MFIs. Except for SHGs promoted by the TMC for implementation of SJSRY, the SHG-bank linkage of the majority of SHGs is limited only to depositing the thrift of SHGs in the bank. In the absence of standardized products manufactured by SHGs and assured markets for their products, survival of their business is doubtful. This is one of the main reasons that banks are shy of providing finance to them. Though some of the SHGs were established five to six years back but they have not reached a take off stage yet due to various factors coming in the way of their scaling up. All SHGs, irrespective of their BPL or APL status, can scale up their activities if they get organized into federations, have tie-ups with financial institutions, technical institutions providing training to set up micro enterprises and business houses to gain from their business acumen in production and marketing of products. For this to happen, the government bodies, NGOs and business houses committed to corporate social responsibility have to come forward to be the torch bearers and lend their support to SHGs to break vicious cycle of poverty.

Mr. Ravi Verma Ms. Rajni Sinha

“Micro-finance – a critical analysis of rural India” Rural is often looked down upon as a not a healthy place to live, where that place is a secluded place for the underprivileged and where only the down trodden people can live. On the other side, micro is a word that has its presence that reflects only the small and the underprivileged. Lack of access to finance is often cited as a key reason why poor people remain poor. This paper will throw light on the Indian rural sector as the emerging and vibrant sector which will take India to fulfill the dream of the developed country. India can be divided into two parts on the basis of development: one is Developed India and other is Undeveloped India, there arises a need of Development of the underdeveloped Area .The research will focus to determine that, what various Factors are contributing to the development of Rural India. It will focus on how the micro finance Institutions can help the people of Rural India, so that they can get the Equal opportunity for the Industrial and Agriculture growth.

Sowmyan Jegatheesan, Sakthi Ganesh, and Praveen Kumar S.

Research study about the role of microfinance institutions in the development of entrepreneurs”

The Case Study is to have its Focus for entrepreneurs who want to run a business and yet can't afford a piece of equipment and merchandise. A research where by providing equipment or merchandise to enable the project to run a self funding profitable project. In turn, A share in the project plus getting the full costs of the asset equipment or merchandise including an interest. So, direct seed finance is not needed to be put in a project. Microfinance is the provision that provides access to various financial services such as credit, savings, micro insurance, remittances, leasing to low-income clients including consumers and the self employed, who traditionally lack access to banking and related services. Its main objective is to provide a permanent access to appropriate financial services including insurance, savings, and fund transfer. As Micro finance becomes more widely accepted and moves into main stream, the supply of services to poor may also increase, improving the efficiency and outreach while lowering the costs.

Priyanka, Richa Verma and Meenu

Microfinance in India The purpose of this study was to understand micro finance in India The main objective of this research paper is analysis to the Microfinance in India as a powerful tool for poverty alleviation. There are many societies, companies, trusts and bodies corporate and such other institutions which are engaged in providing micro finance services to the poor households as a complementary to the banking system. There are two broad approaches that characterize the microfinance sector in India—SHG-bank linkage (SBL) and Microfinance Institutions (MFIs). SBL is a larger model than MFIs in India, contrary to the global practices of other MFIs. Microfinance total loan growth is estimated to have risen by around 30% year on year in fiscal 2012/13 (April-March). The Central Government have felt that since these institutions lack a formal statutory framework for providing such micro finance services, The Micro Finance Institutions (Development and Regulation) Bill, 2012 has passed on 11 February, 2014to provide a statutory framework for the promotion, development, regulation and orderly growth of such Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) and thereby facilitate financial inclusion.

Nishanth P. and Dr. Zakkariya K.A

“Barriers faced by micro, small and medium enterprises in raising finance” Worldwide, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) have been accepted as an engine of economic growth and for promoting equitable development. In developing countries including India, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises sector constitute an important part in its development. In spite of this importance, this sector

face number of constraints like absence of adequate and timely supply of bank finance, difficulties in procuring raw materials, marketing and distribution challenges and non availability of suitable technology. Review of literature found that there exists problem in accessing finance from banks and financial institutions and this problem may differ from region to region, between sectors, or between individual enterprises within a sector. This paper tries to identify the various barriers faced by these units in raising finance and also try to identify the various sources of finance other than banks. The study is based upon the primary data collected from the 200 MSMEs owners in Kozhikode District of Kerala. The data has been analysed with the help of percentage. The study attempts to submit some recommendations to enhance the overall credit accessibility to MSMEs sector

M L Rajeswari K

“Training for staff in micro finance institution for sustainability” Micro finance institution in India was started in the early 1980s with the formation of formal & informal self help groups. This sector had been transformed in to a few such as non-government organization, non-banking finance company, cooperatives, postal savings bank, state owned development banks and most of them started as non-profit organization. SIDBI and NABARD are supplying financial resources to this sector. Today many NGOs are giving support and these factors strengthen micro finance sector in India. NGOs started MFOs which are rooted in the failure of banks to meet the needs of the poor. NGOs offer different kinds of support services like savings, risk management, credit, insurance etc. and minimize risk with group guarantees. In accordance with the transformation or growth in this MF sector, the state of the developing human resources (staff) through training is embryonic with respect to the needs and demands and changes in this sector. According to survey report on HR CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN MFI, April, 2008 issued by micro finance insights in India, people matters are most challenging in comparison to financial and technology matter. After recruitment, the training & capacity building figure out as a predominant factor in preventing turn over in MFI. Training is important for sustainability. Training consists of developing skills of the staff in MFI. The current study figure out the training programs offered by Management institutions, training centers etc. and discusses the need for training and finally concludes with suggested skills which are important for sustainability of MFI.

Vivek kumar Tripathi

“Microfinance - evolution, and microfinance-growth of India” The present paper highlights the microfinance & evaluates the position of microfinance. The concept of microfinance is not new in India. Traditionally, people have saved with and taken small loans from individuals and groups within the context of self-help to start businesses or farming ventures. Majority of poor are excluded from financial services. Microfinance is a programme to support the poor rural people to pay its debt and maintain social and economic status in the villages. Microfinance is an important tool for improving the standard of living of poor. Inspire of many organizations of microfinance, microfinance is not sufficient in India. The study explores some suggestions to make microfinance more effective. The potential for growing micro finance institutions in India is very high. Microfinance market in India is expected to grow rapidly, supported by government of India’s initiatives to achieve greater financial inclusion, and growth in the country’s unorganized but priority sector. Microfinance has evolved rapidly into a global movement dedicated to providing access to a range of financial services to poor and nearpoor households. The organizations that

provide these services, known as Microfinance institutions (MFIs) may operate as formal micro banks, non-bank financial institutions, non-governmental organizations, or community-based financial institutions. These providers offer a range of financial services from small business loans to savings accounts, money transfers, insurance, and consumer loans. Growth of the microfinance industry, however, the microfinance is important as a minimum condition for achieving these social missions. Major Cross-section can have benefit if this sector will grow in its fastest pace. On the basis of growth and evolution related to microfinance, the study predicts the new agenda for future. The microfinance industry being very small in terms of value added to the Indian financial sector. It examines the experience, of India, which has one of the largest microfinance sectors in the world. Globally, over a billion poor people are still without access to formal financial services. Some 200 million of these people live in India. Microfinance, the provision of a wide range of financial services to poor people, has proved a very successful way of providing immensely valuable services to poor people on a sustainable basis. Access to financial services has allowed many families throughout the developing world. It is incontestable that an efficient and effective microfinance system is essential for building a sustained for Economic growth. The Indian Government should find an avenue for creation of awareness on how microfinance can benefit from loans and monitors closely to ensure disbursement of loans and grants to entrepreneurs.

Tiwari, A. (2012)

“Is microfinance working for what it is meant to be? A comparative study on Bangladesh and India” Conducts a comparative study between India and Bangladesh in terms of loan lend by institutes to customers, clientele, and financial sustainability of MFIs in order to understand how MFIs in India are performing as against those MFIs in Bangladesh as it is considered to be the originator of microfinance. The findings discover that no doubt Indian MFIs are more profitable and operating more efficiently than those in Bangladesh.

Padama K. M. S. et al. (2012)

“Microfinance and its risk management practices in India: A conceptual study” Stated about the framework to help MFIs to adopt the systematic way of risk management practices in order to capitalize new opportunities and also to minimize the risks in their operations. The finding shows the micro finance industry has experienced dramatic growth during the last two decades, in general and the last decade, in particular. Such growth is not only sought by many MFIs but also needed in most countries because the un-served and undeserved market continues to remain large. However, pursuit of growth in terms of breadth, depth and scope of outreach does not mean that MFIs can ignore risk management.

Kulshrestha, A. C. (2011)

“measuring the unorganized sector in India”, Review of income and wealth”, Examines the problem of measuring the unorganized sector and explains the approach taken by the Indian Central Statistical Office in terms of the employment it generates and its contribution to value added. The finding shows that it is essential to strengthen surveys on informal sector activities to provide more reliable information in order to facilitate a proper analysis of the dynamics of unorganized sector

Regi, E. M. (2011)

“Microfinance and women empowerment: evidence from field study”, Journal of Rural Development, examines the empowerment impact of microfinance program of neighborhood groups (NHGs) in Kerala

and is based on primary data collected from 200 respondents in 30 (NHGs) functioning in 11 Gram panchayats in Nilambur block in Kerala. The finding revealed that part from providing savings and credit to its members; NHGs were instrumental in bringing desired social change among the members. The ability to contribute to household income as a result of the credit access and increased income from income generating activities helped the members to get respected in their family and community as well. This acceptance in turn helped to gain confidence, increased role in household decision-making, and control over resources, ability to freely interact with members of the group as well as outsiders, ability to deal with adversities and involvement in community activities

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